

The Influence of Code Switching and Code Mixing in Teaching and Learning Process at the Institute of Adult Education Mwanza Campus

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Abstract	Original Research Article
<p>This paper embarks on the influence of code switching and code mixing in the teaching and learning process in adult learning centers. This paper opted for code switching and mixing since they are well-known traits in the speech pattern of the average bilingual and multilingual in any society in Tanzania. Thus this study attempts to analyze the influence of code switching and code mixing in the teaching and learning process using the Development Interdependence Hypothesis propounded by Cummis (1978) specifically analyzing the influence and reasons why code switching and mixing in the teaching and learning process. Data collection included interviews where students and facilitators were interviewed as well and observations were conducted during ongoing classroom activities such as teaching, seminar presentation and discussions. The recommendation and suggestions on the impact of code switching and mixing have been conducted to give an overall description of this phenomenon.</p> <p>Keywords: Code Switching, Code Mixing, Learning Process, Adult Learning Centers, Teaching and Learning</p>	

INTRODUCTION

(Poplack, 2000)states that code switching is the alternation of two languages within a single discourse, sentence or constituent. In an educational context, code switching is defined as the practice of switching between a primary and a secondary language or discourse (Coffey, 2008). It is common among the bilingual and multilingual communities in Africa, India and, among immigrants in Europe and America. Code Switching (CS) is far from homogeneous and the actual linguistic behaviour involved varies depending on the sociolinguistic circumstances. Also the term code switching refers to the use of two different languages within the same conversational episode (Halmar, 2004 as cited Josefsson, 2010). Code switching is a widely observed phenomenon in multilingual and multicultural communities especially in foreign language teaching (Waris, 2012). Code switching is the one of alternative ways to bilingual two or more languages in the same conversation. Code mixing is the change of one language to another within the same utterance or in the same oral/ written text. It is a common phenomenon in societies in which two or more languages are used. (Yee Ho,2007). Code mixing as the term refers to the use of one or more languages for the consistent transfer of linguistic units from one language into another, and by such a language mixture developing a new restricted or not-so-restricted code of linguistic interaction. (Nusjam 2004). Muysken (2000) uses the term ‘code-mixing’ to describe a situation where there is a combination of lexical and grammatical features of distinct languages in one sentence. It should be mentioned that many individuals mix sentences in their daily conversations. Also,

In adult learning centers, facilitators and learners do code switch and mix in and outside the lecture rooms for clarification and an easy learning process, thus This study, therefore, attempts to analyze the influence of code switching and code mixing in the teaching and learning process using Developmental Interdependence Hypothesis by Cummis (1978) that a learner’s competence in a second language

is partly dependent on the level of competence already achieved in language one (L1) since bilinguals are able to transfer skills from language one to language two hence this lead on code switching and mixing in teaching and learning process. The aim of the study is to establish the positive sides of code switching and code mixing, especially in facilitating modules written in the English language.

PURPOSE OF THIS STUDY

The main objective of this study is to analyze the influence of code switching and code mixing in the teaching and learning process on the IAE Mwanza campus.

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES OF THIS STUDY

- i. To explain the reasons why learners/facilitators switch and mix in the teaching and learning process
- ii. To recommend the impact of code switching and code mixing in the teaching and learning process at the IAE-Mwanza Campus

THEORETICAL LITERATURE REVIEW

This study is guided by the developmental interdependence hypothesis propounded by Cummins (1978) proposes that the development of competence in a second language (L2) is partially a function of the type of competence already developed in L1 at the time when intensive exposure to L2 begins. This implies that, if language one is highly developed then language two is likely to be developed adequately. However, if language one degree of development is low, consequently it will affect learning language two. The theory is supported by other authors who argue that language proficiency has a direct influence on language two achievements. (Bild and Swain, 1989). In this study, therefore, this theory was very useful to link on the interference of Kiswahili as learners' first language in learning different subjects facilitated in English as their second language

RELATED LITERATURE REVIEW

Factors influencing Code Switching

Muthusamy et al (2020) in their study elaborated on factors that influence code switching and mixing where participants stated different reasons for why they resorted to code switching in their interactions. Factors affecting code switching extracted from the interviews with the participants are as follows: The lack of competence in the second language, preserving privacy, the ease of speaking in one's own language, avoiding ambiguity and misunderstanding, the lack of similar words in English, unawareness of the equivalent English term or phrase, bridging the gaps while speaking, showing intimacy, adding emphasis, Drawing attention, and pragmatic reasons.

Also Heller as cited in Jourdan and Tuite (2006) maintains that language is looked at as a set of resources which are socially distributed. Speakers have to act within certain kinds of structural constraints. In multilingual communities, the practice of code switching reveals values attached to each code that members do not articulate through structured interactions. Depending on the historical or cultural contexts, codes may be differently valued and members may display ambivalent feelings towards one or more of these codes in their everyday speech practices. Therefore, children acquire values associated with each code through participation in social activities involving code selection and cultural knowledge impacts their acquisition of codes. It is hence such code choices in varied social contexts and activities in the school that the current research wanted to focus on. The social contexts and interactions are useful for that is where the students can put the language learnt in class to practice.

Johansson (2004) also conducted a research on CS and CM in a Swedish high school. From the findings she concluded that tags are mixed with other codes, entire phrases are switched. This is to compensate for deficiencies in one language. A more objective research was recommended to give a clear picture on how, when and why students code switch. However, research conducted by Muthuuri (2002) code switching in multilingual community focusing on the choice between English, Kiswahili, and local languages. He identified stylistic functions, social functions and social symbolism. His theoretical framework was based on Giles' Speech Accommodation theory, Scotton's Negotiation Principles and Gumperz's Conversational Functions Model. The author found that Kiswahili and mother tongue were the dominant language of everyday interaction, for national and ethnic solidarity. English was used for detachment,

alienation and higher status. Both Gumperz's and Giles' theory was important to the current study.

Reasons for Using Code Switching and Code Mixing

The reasons for using code switching and code mixing such as lack of knowledge of one language or lack of facility in that language on a certain subject. The second reason for code switching is its use including certain persons present from apportion of conversations. It is known that those persons do not know the language used for switching. While the third reason uses code switching is also used as a stylistic device is to indicate a change in the tone of his conversation, at a certain point or to signal the introduction of a subject more or less formal than what had been under discussion. (Girsang, 2020)

Girsang (2020) analyzing and classified the types of Code Switching and Code Mixing, the researcher identified the following reasons why the producer used these English-Indonesian Codes Switching and Codes mixing in Jakarta television advertisements. The writer analyses the reasons for using Code Mixing and Code Switching based on Hoffman's theory (1991:116). There are a number of reasons for using Code Mixing and Code Switching in conversation. The reasons are analyzed as follows: A. Talking About Particular Topic People sometimes prefer to talk about a particular topic in one language rather than in another. Sometimes, the speaker feels free and more comfortable to express his/her emotional feelings in a language that is not his/her everyday language.

From the examples above, the words in the sentences were such examples of Code Mixing that talking about certain topic reasons. They were mixed with Indonesian to discuss a particular topic/ product to promote. In example (1) the speaker uses the phrase 'master mom' because the topic is about the really dirty clothes that are used by children and only the master mom who uses 'Soklin' is able to clean the dirty clothes. In example (2) the speaker uses the words 'Bookingnya' and 'Travelingnya' because the topic is talking about a particular topic about travelling business where the two words is familiar used to book tickets and do travelling. Further, in example number (3) the speaker uses the word 'sale' because the topic is about a business matter that talks about Lazada as a place to sell something. So the word 'Sale' in English is fit to replace the Indonesia word 'berjualan'. Quoting Somebody Else A speaker switches or mixes code to quote a famous expression, proverb or saying of some well-known figure. The switch and mix involve just the words that the speaker is claiming the quoted person said. The switch and the mix are like a set of quotation mark. In this research, the writer did not find the Code Mixing and Code Switching because of Quoting Somebody Else. Being Emphatic about Something (Express Solidarity) As usually, when someone who is talking using a language that is not his native language suddenly wants to be emphatic about something, he either intentionally or unintentionally, will mix or switch from his second language to his first language, in the other hand, he felt more convenient to be emphatic in his second language rather than in his first language.

Example: 1. Ah...,dadu mereka luar biasa singaku hilang. It's alright baby, kita punya dadu yang paling hebat.

From the example above, the phrase 'I like' and the sentences 'It's alright baby' and I love it' were spoken because of the speaker intentionally switched from his first language (Indonesian) to his second language (English). Besides, it was also caused that she felt more convenient to be emphatic

(Josefsson, 2010) one reason for teachers' code switching has to do with understanding, such as when teachers want to convey or check the meaning of words or sentences, or when explaining grammar. Another occasion when teachers code-switch to the L1 is when they are giving instructions and organizing tasks. A third occasion is where the L1 feels more 'real' than the L2. An example of this can be when the teacher is dealing with disciplinary problems in the classroom and chooses to give reprimands in the L1 since it often seems more serious than if the reprimand is given in the L2. Another example might be when the teacher wants to establish personal contact with a student or praise a student's work, since the praise often seems more real when it is said in the L1 instead of the L2

Muthuuri (2002) conducted research on code switching relevant to the current study. Muthuuri's research was on code switching among Kenyatta University's multilingual community focusing on the choice between English, Kiswahili, and local languages. He identified stylistic functions, social functions and social symbolism.

Nthinga (2003) looked at the functions of code switching in pre-primary classroom discourse. Her work was concerned with how CS aids the teaching process. It focused on pre-primary classroom discourse in Kasarani division, Nairobi. She found from the research that CS was a normal practice out of necessity so that a teacher would be understood, and that Kenya is a multilingual society and CS is an upshot of the same. The study also revealed that English and other languages can co-exist. According to Muthwii.

The Influence of Code Switching and Code Mixing

Code switching could be one of the factors influencing students' performance in oral and written discourse. The influence of CS on the student's performance in English was more evident in their oral performance than written performance. The most prevalent influence is the direct use of Dholuo words at intra-sentential level. Lexical errors in the form of direct translation were the most prevalent

in oral performance. This was followed by syntactic errors (wrong grammar) and lastly, phonetic errors could only be observed in written work whereas there were no prosodic errors (wrong intonation/stress) recorded. However, the English language performance of the majority of the students was not affected by code switching as suggested by the relatively small percentage of errors established. The student's performance as a result of CS manifested indirectly mostly in terms of lack of fluency, wordiness and/or speaking difficulties. (Akumu,2014)

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study relied on a qualitative approach. This method is also called naturalistic research because the research is done in a natural setting. Sugiono (2009:15) states that descriptive qualitative research is a research method that used to search the objects in natural setting which is the researcher is a key instrument, getting sampling by purposive and snowball, data is analyzed qualitatively and the result of the research generally about language and meaning. The aim of descriptive design in this study was to collect information on when, how and why facilitators and students do code switch and mix in teaching and learning processes in adult education learning centers.

Area of Study

The study was carried out at the Institute of Adult Education Mwanza campus which is allocated in the Mwanza region, Nyamagana district in Luchelele ward at the shore of Lake Victoria, it is the campus where students pursue their studies in Certificate of Adult Education and community development as well as Diploma in Adult education and community development program full-time (conventional). The researcher decided to choose the IAE Mwanza campus as the area of her study because she is familiar with the place and among the facilitator who teach different subjects in English such as English grammar, Psychology, Basics of research and other subjects as the way of teaching and she switches and mixes so that learners can understand the lesson well. Ingggris (2017) in his journal said that many teachers make code mixing and code switching in different levels of students, topic and participants, but in reality, teachers dominantly make code switching in advance of students than at low levels.

Target Population

The research targeted students and facilitators of the IAE-Mwanza campus. For this reason, the study involved students pursuing a Basic Technician Certificate in Adult Education and Community Development program graded as level 4, students pursuing a Technician Certificate in Adult Education and Community Development graded as level 5 and students studying for Ordinary Diploma in Adult Education and Community Development graded as level6 program, this formed the target population of the present study.

Sampling Technique

The technique used in this study was systematic sampling technique. According to Denscombe (2010), systematic sampling operates on the same principles of random sampling whereby every population member has an equal chance of being selected but introduces a system whereby samples are chosen based on everything case.

Sample Size and Sampling Procedure

The study used two samples; the facilitator's sample and the students' sample where the researcher sampled 8 facilitators out of 15 and 42 students out of 174 where both purposive and simple random sampling were used to choose the respondents. Purposive sampling was used in choosing IAE facilitators from the entire population and simple random sampling was used in selecting students pursuing both certificate and diploma programs at IAE Mwanza campus. The researcher decided to select the sample given to obtain enough data relating to the study.

Table 1: Sampling Grid

S/N	Type of Respondent	Total Population	Sample Size	Percentage(%)

1	Facilitators	15	8	$8 \times 100 / 50 = 16\%$
2	Students pursuing Basic Technician Certificate program (level4)	11	5	$5 \times 100 / 50 = 10\%$
3	Students pursuing Technician certificate program(level5)	75	18	$18 \times 100 / 50 = 36\%$
4	Students pursuing Ordinary diploma program(level6)	73	19	$19 \times 100 / 50 = 38\%$
Total		174	50	100%

Source: Researcher (2023)

From the above table shows the sample size of 50 respondents used in data collection hence the sample given presented the whole population of the IAE Mwanza campus in the present study.

Data Collection Techniques

In order to obtain a wide range of information for the purpose of the study, two methods of data collection were used namely; interview and observation schedule. Through interviews, the researcher intended to obtain the respondents' experience, opinions and knowledge on the subject of inquiry while through observation schedule a researcher intended to obtain information by investigating how respondents code switch and mix in the teaching and learning process

Interview

This is a face-to-face interaction between a researcher and the respondents on to one basis (Enon, 2018). This instrument was administered to the IAE facilitators and learners. The respondent's views on why they code switch and mix in teaching and learning also explained how code switch and mix influence the teaching and learning process. The technique provides flexibility for respondents to provide detailed information to express their views.

Observation Schedule

Kothari (2009) explains that under the observation method, information is sought by way of the investigator's own direct observation without asking from the respondent. The main advantage cited by the author is that subjective bias is eliminated if it is done accurately, and the information obtained relates to what is currently happening; thus it is not complicated by either past behaviour or future intentions. This tool was used to collect data on Code mixing and switching during facilitation, seminar presentation and discussion.

Data Analysis Procedure

All information that was collected from interviews and observation schedule were subjected to content analysis which involved identifying coherent and important examples, themes and patterns in data collected from the fieldwork. The qualitative approach therefore was analyzed through thematic analysis where data were categorized according to their relevant themes and patterns developed accordingly.

Findings

In this section a researcher presents the findings of the interviews with eight facilitators named in alphabet A-H, the main purpose of this interview was to investigate facilitators' own thoughts about code switching and mixing, to find out which language is easier when teaching in the classroom and the subject/module do they teach to students pursuing basic certificate, technician certificate and ordinary diploma at the IAE Mwanza campus as well as the reasons why do they code switch and mix during teaching process

questions given (see Appendix 1), Facilitators responded to the interview questions given as follows;

Subjects/Modules Do Facilitators Teach/Facilitate

Eight facilitators are teaching modules written in English, two of them are teaching Kiswahili and other modules written in English, therefore they said that code-switching and mixing are something that they use in their teaching and the situation that very often came up first as an example of situations in which they tend to code-switch or mix in elaborating different topics.

Language that is Easier when Teaching in the Classroom

Facilitators who teach modules in English at the IAE campus responded to the interview question “which language is easier when teaching in the classroom? they responded that English is not their first language hence they term it as a foreign language so it is not much easier for them to use in the teaching process. Hence they code switch and mix with Kiswahili as their first language for ease of teaching/learning process. Three of the facilitators elaborated the following;

Facilitator A elaborated, *I’m professional in linguistics and when I am teaching English grammar I use English though I code mix to elaborate some difficult vocabularies to students who study English in level5”*

Facilitator B, *I have been teaching information technologies (IT) modules for more than two years, I do code switch and mix into Kiswahili to clarify how to operate and maintain a computer this helps students to understand the topic otherwise most students cannot understand well the lesson.*

Facilitator C explained that *teaching philosophical ideas to students is not easy hence I code switch in elaborating the topic on what philosophers said and its contribution to education*

From the above response, shows that Kiswahili is used as the language in teaching modules written in English as most facilitators do code switch and mix in the classroom.

Learners Code Switch/Mix in Seminar Presentations

Eight respondents agreed that most students code switch and mix in seminar presentations except modules written in Kiswahili, through interview below are some of the responses from the facilitators;

Facilitator C responded to the interview questions that *“During the session of management of literacy classes seminar presentation in the class of level six in the first semester the date of October 2023, one of the students failed to explain the topic about management skills hence he started explaining in Kiswahili where some of the students were laughing because the presenter failed and code switched to Kiswahili language which is his L1” he continued that, these they prefer Kiswahili to English as you can see even in examinations normally they fail.*

Facilitator F: *as a facilitator in level4 facilitating Basics of adult facilitation I have experienced students code switch and mix some vocabularies using Kiswahili in seminar presentation, I wish to advise the government to change the curriculum so as Kiswahili should be the medium of instruction from primary level to the university.*

From the above response, shows that Kiswahili is used as the language in teaching modules written in English as most facilitators do code switch and mix in the classroom.

Reasons for Code Switching and Mixing in the Teaching and Learning Process

Through the interview, facilitators were asked to explain the reasons why do code switch and mix in the classroom during the teaching process;

Code-Switching for Comprehending Knowledge

One situation of code-switching that most facilitators elaborated that they do code-switch to easy learning and make sure that the students understood the lesson thus they use Kiswahili sometimes when giving instructions given in English.

To Make Meaning Clear

Facilitators through interview explained that they make code switching in the class to make meaning clear and to transfer the knowledge to students in an efficient way.

The Facilitators' Awareness of their Own Code-Switching and Mixing

Most facilitators said that their code-switching or mixing was improvised rather than planned. Teachers A, C, D and H said it depended very much on the different situations and that they code switched/mixed if they felt the situation required it. The only code-switching/mixing situation they were very aware of and actually planned was teaching grammar. Although all of the teachers in the interviews seemed to think that they knew when they tended to code-switch and mix, most of them actually code-switch and mixed in more situations during the observations than they mentioned in the interviews. This suggests that the facilitators' willingness to provide comprehensible information is an important reason for code-switching/mixing and that facilitators' ability to adapt to different situations in the classroom is important to them.

Student's Views on the Reasons why they Code Switch and Mix

Students who were interviewed explained that they use code switching and mixing in order to;

To Make Clarification on a Certain Concept

This is normally done when making seminar presentations to the modules taught in English, one of student explained that during presentation session, she normally code switch and mix in order to clarify on a certain point for more understanding. As follows: Respondent A explained that *"Madam there are some statements that are quite difficult to explain in English so we explain in Kiswahili for clarification hence every student can understand what we are presenting for, if the statement is not well clarified some of students start shouting in the classroom that they don't understand what we are present for, this lead us to code switch and mix using Kiswahili as our L1"* she continued *"ninapenda kueleza kwa kutumia Kiswahili ili wanafunzi wenzangu waelewe kile nachokisema (I like using Kiswahili so as my fellow students could understand what am presenting for)*

Respondent B, also added that, *we do code switch to make our fellow students understand what we present, some modules have difficult vocabularies.*

From the above, it shows students at IAE Mwanza campus code switch and mix in order to make other college mate to understand what is being discussed.

Lack of English Vocabularies

Some of the students who were interviewed elaborated that they lack English vocabulary therefore they code switch and mix in Kiswahili as their L1 in order to fulfill the learning gap. This is because they prefer Kiswahili in their daily activities more than English, they only start using English when they start learning one of the interviewees said *"Hatuna misamiati ya kutosha ya Kingereza kwa sababu hatukizungumzi kila mara kama Kiswahili, pia sio lugha yetu (We don't have more English vocabularies because we don't use English always as Kiswahili our language)"*

The College Context

The students who study in certificate programs his of the opinion that the highest frequency of use of Kiswahili is because the students find the environment free of strict supervision on language use, he said that when he was in secondary school, he was obliged to speak English as it was strict and all the school compound labelled with **SPEAK ENGLISH** banners, but here at IAE campus there is no such restrictions that's why normally they code switch and mix with Kiswahili in and outside the classroom.

To Ensure a Better Understanding

Some students explained that their facilitators code switch and mix during the teaching process to diverse linguistics backgrounds of the learners and ensure better understanding. They added that he code switch and mix to enhance the learning experience

by promoting comprehension and engagement.

Classroom Observations

Facilitators use Kiswahili in the classroom to; task instructions by explain what the students are going to do in the classroom, to explain and translate grammar to students, to explain certain phrases or words and to show emotions and give advice to students who fail different examination and tests in the classroom.

Also students use Kiswahili as their first language to make discussion on different task/assignments given by their facilitators, to make clarifications on the topic during seminar presentation, to argue with their fellow students on the given instructions and to communicate with their facilitators on the difficult given topics.

Generally, a researcher noticed that facilitators and students at the IAE Mwanza campus do code switch and mix English with Kiswahili language in teaching and learning process according to Cummins (1978), the theory states that a learner's competence in a second language is partly dependent on the level of competence already achieved in language one (L1) since bilinguals are able to transfer skills from language one to language two. This implies that, if language one is highly developed then language two is likely to be developed adequately. However, if language one degree of development is low, it will affect learning language two in their L1

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Students' views on this, code switching and mixing can create a positive learning environment by fostering inclusivity and cultural sensitivity also acknowledging and respecting the linguistic diversity of learners, leading to better participation and knowledge retention.

Most students recommended that it is essential to promote a multilingual learning environment that embraces different languages and encourages learners to use their preferred language for effective communication hence multilingual resources can further support the learning process.

Facilitators agreed that you can't separate the teaching and learning process from code mixing and switching in the IAE-Mwanza campus since most students' L1 is Kiswahili. If you facilitate without code switching or mixing, none of them will capture the lesson taught.

Summary of Findings

From data given above, several findings come forth that Code switching and mixing are highly used at the IAE-Mwanza campus by both facilitators and learners, both facilitators and learners use code switching and mixing in the teaching and learning process, L1 which is Kiswahili skills can be transferred to L2 which is English in the teaching and learning process, code switching and code mixing is unavoidable in daily interaction since most of the teachers and learners code mix and switch to Kiswahili as their L1 in teaching and learning.

CONCLUSION

The influence of code switching and mixing in teaching and learning process at the Institute of Adult Education Mwanza campus was discussed in this paper where it is proved that most facilitators code switch and mix when teaching students in the classroom so as to ease teaching process as well as students in their daily learning process code switch and mix to ensure better understanding.

RECOMMENDATIONS

From the findings of this study, it is evident that code switching and mixing is inevitable in teaching and learning process therefore it is recommended that scholars should keep in mind that code switching and mixing is the best way of easy teaching and learning process.

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1. Interview Guide for Facilitators

Thank you very much for having accepted to participate in this exercise. My name is Alfredina Fredinand. I am an assistant lecturer at the Institute of Adult Education Mwanza campus carrying out my study on the **Influence of code switching and code mixing in the teaching and learning process at IAE-Mwanza campus**. The information that you will provide to me will be treated in confidentiality and only used for educational purposes. Feel free for any inquiry

1. What subjects do you teach?
2. Which language is easier when teaching in the classroom
3. In the teaching process, do you code switch/mix?
4. Are your learners code-switch/mix when making seminar presentations?
5. What are the reasons for code switching and mixing in teaching and learning processes?
6. What is the influence of code switching and mixing in the teaching and learning process?

Appendix 2. Interview Guide for Learners

Thank you very much for having accepted to participate in this exercise. My name is Alfredina Fredinand. I am an assistant lecturer at the Institute of Adult Education Mwanza campus carrying out my study on the **Influence of code switching and code mixing in the**

teaching and learning process. The information that you will provide to me will be treated in confidentiality and only used for educational purposes. Feel free for any inquiry

1. Which language do you prefer in the teaching and learning process?
2. In the learning process, do you code switch/mix?
3. Do your facilitators code switch/mix when facilitating?
4. Why do you code switch and mix when learning?
5. What is the influence of code switching and mixing in the learning process?

The researcher observed the following tactics relating to this study:

1. Observing the teaching process in the classroom
2. Listening to the seminar presentation in the classroom
3. Listening to conversations among learners on which language they use mostly in and out of the classroom.

Observing the interference of L1 in L2 especially in sentence structure.